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Businesses in the Construction Sector in OECD Countries

The OECD calculates the number of businesses in the construction sector. The data refers to micro, small, medium, and large enterprises.

Businesses in the Construction Sector in OECD Countries in 2022. The analysis of data related to the number of businesses in the construction sector in OECD countries for the year 2022 reveals significant differences among nations, reflecting various economic, demographic, and infrastructural development dynamics. France leads the ranking with 563,164 businesses, followed by Italy with 504,219 and Poland with 413,922. This high number of businesses in France and Italy can be attributed to their historical presence of small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) in the construction sector, which continue to thrive due to a combination of robust domestic demand, SME support policies, and public infrastructure investments. Poland, which has experienced notable economic growth in recent decades, is investing heavily in infrastructure and residential construction projects, supported by European Union funds. Spain, with 400,008 businesses, shows the recovery of a sector that suffered heavily during the 2008 financial crisis. Economic recovery and renewed interest in real estate and tourism development have stimulated growth in the construction sector. Germany, with 382,442 businesses, reflects a solid industrial and infrastructural base, with a strong emphasis on quality and innovation. Despite having fewer businesses compared to other large European countries, German enterprises tend to be larger and better capitalized. Turkey, with 281,206 businesses, demonstrates a rapidly expanding construction sector, driven by a building boom and large government-sponsored infrastructure projects. Urban growth and the need for new housing and infrastructure support the proliferation of businesses in the sector. The Netherlands, with 254,417 businesses, benefits from a combination of residential development and sustainable infrastructure projects, with particular attention to technological innovation and sustainability. Countries like the Czech Republic and Belgium, with 193,715 and 135,699 businesses respectively, reflect stable growth in the construction sector, supported by expanding economies and favorable government policies. Hungary, with 131,492 businesses, shows similar growth, supported by foreign investments and infrastructure development programs. In Slovakia, with 121,126 businesses, the construction sector is expanding, supported by European investments and growing domestic demand. Sweden, with 104,128 businesses, and Portugal, with 102,474 businesses, show robust construction sectors, supported by housing policies and sustainable infrastructure investments. Romania, with 100,670 businesses, demonstrates a growing construction sector, supported by European funds and increasing demand for modern infrastructure. Israel, with 79,027 businesses, shows a dynamic construction sector, driven by demographic growth and urban development. Ireland, with 70,457 businesses, benefits from robust economic growth and a construction boom fueled by demand for new housing and infrastructure. Greece, with 69,693 businesses, is gradually recovering after years of economic crisis, with a slowly recovering construction sector. Norway, with 59,442 businesses, and Finland,

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with 56,061 businesses, show stable construction sectors, supported by strong economies and continuous demand for modern infrastructure. Austria, with 41,399 businesses, reflects a well-developed and highly regulated construction sector. Smaller countries like Lithuania, with 39,111 businesses, and Denmark, with 36,808 businesses, show active construction sectors, supported by sustainable development policies and growing economies. Croatia, with 28,573 businesses, demonstrates an expanding construction sector, driven by tourism and infrastructure investments. Costa Rica, with 24,559 businesses, and Slovenia, with 22,758 businesses, show dynamic construction sectors, supported by growing domestic demand and foreign investments. Bulgaria, with 22,577 businesses, reflects steady growth, supported by European investments. Switzerland, with 22,332 businesses, demonstrates a highly developed and regulated construction sector, with an emphasis on quality and innovation. Estonia, with 16,106 businesses, shows a growing construction sector, driven by technological and infrastructural investments. Countries like Serbia, with 15,576 businesses, and Latvia, with 10,405 businesses, reflect stable growth, supported by government policies and foreign investments. Cyprus, with 10,030 businesses, shows an expanding construction sector, driven by tourism and foreign investments. Malta, with 5,957 businesses, and North Macedonia, with 5,725 businesses, demonstrate small but growing construction sectors, supported by local demand and foreign investments. Bosnia and Herzegovina, with 5,522 businesses, shows a developing construction sector, supported by growing demand for modern infrastructure. Luxembourg, with 4,493 businesses, reflects a small but highly developed construction sector, with an emphasis on high-quality and innovative projects.

Businesses in the Construction Sector in OECD Countries Between 2005 and 2022. The analysis of data related to the number of businesses in the construction sector in OECD countries between 2005 and 2022 reveals significant trends, with notable variations in both absolute and percentage terms. The most striking case is Ireland, which saw an extraordinary increase of 9195.12%, from 758 to 70,457 businesses. This massive increase can be attributed to the country's strong economic growth, post-financial crisis recovery, and attraction of foreign investments that have stimulated the construction sector, particularly in real estate and infrastructure. Slovakia recorded an impressive growth of 2940.31%, from 3,984 to 121,126 businesses. This increase is likely due to European investments and government policies aimed at improving infrastructure, as well as increased demand for residential and commercial construction. Estonia also saw notable growth of 263.24%, increasing from 4,434 to 16,106 businesses, reflecting rapid modernization and a business-friendly environment that has attracted investments in the construction sector. The Netherlands and Lithuania showed significant growth of 233.46% and 223.95% respectively. The Netherlands, growing from 76,295 to 254,417 businesses, demonstrates how an advanced economy and well-developed infrastructure can support robust expansion in the construction sector. Lithuania, from 12,073 to 39,111 businesses, has benefited from favorable policies and increasing demand for new construction projects. Costa Rica recorded an increase of 194.40%, growing from 8,342 to 24,559 businesses. This increase indicates the country's growing economic development and demand for new infrastructure and housing. Poland, with an increase of 151.48%, from 164,597 to 413,922 businesses, reflects one of the fastest-growing economies in Europe, with significant infrastructure investments and a growing real estate market. Latvia and Belgium showed increases of 131.63% and 122.32% respectively. Latvia, growing from 4,492 to 10,405 businesses, and Belgium, from 61,039 to 135,699 businesses, highlight steady growth and economic stability that favor the development of the construction sector. In Hungary, the number of businesses increased by 79.13%, from 73,404 to 131,492, indicating significant sector expansion. Germany saw an increase of 73.60%, from 220,300 to 382,442 businesses, reflecting the

country's solid industrial base and continuous demand for new construction and infrastructure projects. Luxembourg, with an increase of 71.10%, and Bulgaria, with a growth of 70.47%, show how even smaller countries can have robust growth in the construction sector. Finland and Slovenia recorded growth of 65.51% and 59.53% respectively. Finland, with 22,189 new businesses, and Slovenia, with 8,492 new businesses, indicate sustained growth supported by government policies and foreign investments. Austria saw an increase of 59.26%, from 25,994 to 41,399 businesses, demonstrating stable growth and a business-friendly environment. Cyprus and Sweden showed increases of 56.65% and 55.24% respectively. Cyprus, growing from 6,403 to 10,030 businesses, and Sweden, from 67,076 to 104,128 businesses, highlight continuous growth in the construction sector. Norway recorded an increase of 46.77%, from 40,499 to 59,442 businesses, reflecting sustained demand for new construction projects. France saw an increase of 37.67%, from 409,055 to 563,164 businesses. This increase indicates strong domestic demand and government policies that support the construction sector. The Czech Republic recorded a growth of 33.56%, increasing from 145,036 to 193,715 businesses, signaling continuous expansion in the sector. Denmark showed an increase of 18.82%, from 30,978 to 36,808 businesses, reflecting moderate but steady growth. However, some countries saw a decrease in the number of businesses in the construction sector. Italy recorded a decrease of 15.53%, from 596,894 to 504,219 businesses, and Spain saw a reduction of 16.52%, from 479,168 to 400,008 businesses. These decreases can be attributed to economic crises, industrial restructurings, and reduced demand for new construction projects. Portugal saw a decrease of 19.41%, from 127,149 to 102,474 businesses.

Economic Policies to Increase Businesses in the Construction Sector in OECD Countries. Economic policies to develop businesses in the construction sector in OECD countries must be integrated, aimed at stimulating growth, innovation, and sustainability. A crucial aspect is investment in infrastructure, which creates immediate demand for construction and improves long-term competitiveness. Large infrastructure projects such as roads, bridges, and railways not only generate jobs but also modernize transport networks, reduce logistics costs, and incentivize private investments. OECD countries can learn from successful examples like the Netherlands and Germany, where massive infrastructure investments have supported a robust and innovative construction sector. In addition, tax incentives are fundamental to stimulating private investments in construction. Tax credits for renovations and new constructions, tax exemptions for the purchase of sustainable materials, and deductions for research and development expenses can make investing in construction projects more attractive for businesses. In countries like France and Italy, tax incentives for energy renovations have proven effective in promoting sustainability and innovation in the construction sector. Access to credit is another key element. Financial institutions and governments must collaborate to offer low-interest loans and loan guarantees for construction projects. Microfinance programs can help small construction businesses obtain the necessary capital to grow and innovate. Poland and Hungary have successfully implemented such programs, supporting SMEs and stimulating sector growth. At the same time, workforce training is essential. Vocational training programs and apprenticeships develop the skills needed to use new technologies and tackle market challenges. The dual education system in Germany, which combines school education and on-the-job training, is an excellent example of how to prepare workers for the construction sector. Technological innovation is crucial for improving efficiency and competitiveness. Technologies such as 3D printing, drones, artificial intelligence (AI), and the Internet of Things (IoT) can revolutionize construction processes, reducing costs and improving quality. Governments must support innovation through research and development funding, collaborations between universities and industries, and tax incentives for adopting new technologies.

The United Kingdom, for example, has launched initiatives to promote the use of Building Information Modeling (BIM) technology, which improves construction project planning and management. Sustainability must be at the center of policies for the construction sector. Encouraging the use of sustainable building materials, promoting the construction of low-impact buildings, and adopting green building practices can significantly reduce the environmental impact of the sector. Certification programs such as LEED (Leadership in Energy and Environmental Design) can be incentivized through government grants and tax reductions. Countries like Sweden and Denmark are at the forefront of these practices, promoting sustainable buildings and the use of green technologies in the construction sector. Regulation and standards are essential to ensure that construction practices are safe, efficient, and sustainable. Regulations can include strict safety standards, energy efficiency requirements for buildings, and environmental regulations to reduce pollution. Governments must ensure that these regulations are consistently applied and that there are incentives for businesses that exceed minimum standards. Adopting international standards can also help standardize construction practices and facilitate cross-border collaboration. Policies must also specifically support small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs), which play a crucial role in the construction sector but often face significant challenges in terms of market access and investment capacity. Specific policies to support SMEs can include access to public procurement programs, tax incentives, business consultancy, and support for internationalization. Countries like France and Italy have implemented programs to support SMEs in the construction sector, recognizing the importance of these businesses for employment and innovation. International cooperation is fundamental to facilitating the sharing of best practices, innovative technologies, and sustainable business models.

Conclusions. The number of businesses in the construction sector in the considered OECD countries grew on average by 41.92% between 2005 and 2022. The countries that saw the highest growth in the number of construction businesses are Ireland with +9195%, the Slovak Republic with +2940%, and Estonia with +263.24%. At the bottom of the list are Italy with -15.53%, Spain with -16.52%, and Portugal with -19.41%. Italy experienced the most significant absolute loss with -92,675 construction businesses between 2005 and 2022. Overall, the number of construction businesses in the considered OECD countries was 4.33 million units. 50% of construction sector businesses are located in five countries: France, Italy, Poland, Spain, and Germany.

Declarations

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References

Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A. (2021). The innovation-employment nexus in Europe. Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A.(2020). The innovation-employment nexus in Europe. American Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences Research (AJHSSR), 4(11), 166-187.

Leogrande, A., Saponaro, A., Massaro, A., & Galiano, A. M. (2020). A GIS based estimation of quality of life in Italian regions. *American Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences Research (AJHSSR)* e-ISSN.

Costantiello, A., Laureti, L., & Leogrande, A. (2021). The intellectual assets in Europe. *Available at SSRN 3956755*.

Magazzino, C., & Leogrande, A. (2020). Subjective well-being in Italian regions: A panel data approach.

Leogrande, A., Massaro, A., & Galiano, A. M. (2020). The attractiveness of European research systems. *American Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences Research (AJHSSR)*, 4(10), 72-101.

Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A. (2023). The Impact of Research and Development Expenditures on ESG Model in the Global Economy. *Available at SSRN 4414232*.

Leogrande, A. (2023). The Rule of Law in the ESG Framework in the World Economy. *Available at SSRN 4355016*.

Leogrande, A., Massaro, A., & Galiano, A. M. (2020). The impact of R&D investments on corporate performance in European Countries. *American Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences Research (AJHSSR)*, 4(7), 186-201.

Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A. (2023). The Role of Political Stability in the Context of ESG Models at World Level. *Available at SSRN 4406997*.

Leogrande, A., Laureti, L., & Costantiello, A. (2022). The Innovation Index in Europe. *Available at SSRN 4091597*.

Laureti, L., Costantiello, A., Matarrese, M., & Leogrande, A. (2022). Enterprises Providing ICT Training in Europe. *Available at SSRN 4021150*.

Leogrande, A., & Costantiello, A. (2023). The Labor Force Participation Rate in the Context of ESG Models at World Level. *Available at SSRN 4466452*.

Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A. (2023). The Impact of Voice and Accountability in the ESG Framework in a Global Perspective. *Available at SSRN 4398483*.

Laureti, L., Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A. (2023). The Role of Government Effectiveness in the Light of ESG Data at Global Level. *Available at SSRN 4324938*.

Costantiello, A., Laureti, L., Leogrande, A., & Matarrese, M. (2021). The Innovation Linkages in Europe. *Available at SSRN 3983218*.

Laureti, L., Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A. (2022). Satisfaction with the Environmental Condition in the Italian Regions between 2004 and 2020. *Available at SSRN 4061708*.

Laureti, L., Costantiello, A., Matarrese, M., & Leogrande, A. (2022). Foreign Doctorate Students in Europe. *Available at SSRN 4032975*.

Laureti, L., Costantiello, A., Matarrese, M., & Leogrande, A. (2022). The Employment in Innovative Enterprises in Europe. *Available at SSRN 4010098*.

Leogrande, A., Costantiello, A., Laureti, L., & Leogrande, D. (2021). The Determinants of Landscape and Cultural Heritage Among Italian Regions in the Period 2004-2019. *Available at SSRN 3971174*.

Leogrande, A., Massaro, A., & Galiano, A. M. (2020). The Determinants of Innovation in European Countries in the period 2010-2019. *American Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences Research (AJHSSR)*, 4(8), 91-126.

Ferri, G., & Leogrande, A. (2015). Was the Crisis due to a shift from stakeholder to shareholder finance? Surveying the debate.

Laureti, L., Costantiello, A., Massaro, A., & Leogrande, A. (2024). The Role of Renewable Energy Consumption in Promoting Sustainability and Circular Economy: A Data-Driven Analysis. In *Data-Driven Intelligent Business Sustainability* (pp. 360-386). IGI Global.

Leogrande, A., & Costantiello, A. (2023). The Role of GDP Growth in the ESG Approach at World Level. *Available at SSRN 4434206*.

Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A. (2023). The Regulatory Quality and ESG Model at World Level. *Available at SSRN 4388957*.

Leogrande, A., Magaletti, N., Cosoli, G., & Massaro, A. (2022). Fixed Broadband Take-Up in Europe. *Available at SSRN 4034298*.

Leogrande, A., Costantiello, A., Laureti, L., & Leogrande, D. (2021). The Determinants of Design Applications in Europe. *Available at SSRN 3956853*.

Laureti, L., Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A. (2021). THE DETERMINANTS OF FIRM INVESTMENTS IN RESEARCH AND DEVELOPMENT. In *IAI ACADEMIC CONFERENCE PROCEEDINGS Education and Social Sciences Business and Economics* (pp. 55-67).

Appendix

Number of Construction Enterprises in OECD Countries (2022)

Percentage Change in Number of Construction Enterprises (2005-2022) in OECD Countries